

HOW VARIOUS UNCERTAINTIES AND ASSUMPTIONS AFFECT B-BASIS ALLOWABLES DEVELOPMENT

C. Rousseau

Structural Analysis, Lockheed Martin Aeronautics Co., Fort Worth, TX, USA

(carl.q.rousseau@lmco.com)

Keywords: *composite material, B-basis strength, allowable, test method, failure mode, failure criteria, length scale*

1 Introduction

Statistics for B-basis¹ allowables development should reflect the fundamental failure modes observed in testing, and must be tailored to fit the particular strength analysis methodology being used. The definition of what is a “fundamental failure mode” in composite material behavior is a critical issue that remains a point of contention and disagreement. This issue has, for years, been confounded by coupon test method limitations and biases, but modern test methods and high quality material are beginning to allow this problem to be unraveled. The fact that design allowable strengths must be matched to the failure criteria used in a particular company- or part-specific strength analysis methodology is not widely discussed or understood. Thus, the objective of this paper is to demonstrate the complexity of test-method-induced effects on B-basis allowable strengths, and how that interacts with failure mode definitions and length-scale/failure criteria-specific issues to influence the reliability and accuracy of composite strength predictions. This paper is divided into separate discussions of failure mode definition, test method issues associated with several key failure modes, and the interaction of failure criteria choice with B-basis allowables development. These issues will be illustrated with a few particular strength properties, using a generic carbon/epoxy tape material.

2 Failure Mode Definitions

Commonly-accepted continuous-fiber carbon tape composite failure modes are listed in Table 1.

¹ B-basis statistical strength is defined as a 95% lower confidence bound for the 10th percentile of the strength population (95% confidence that 9 out of 10 samples are at least this strong) [1].

Certain differences of opinion exist regarding the exact nature of resin-dominated failure modes and how best to characterize them. Fundamentally, the question is one of scale: do you apply failure criteria at the constituent, ply, laminate, or structural level? Three cases that illustrate the complexity of this issue are notched and unnotched fiber-dominated compressive strength, 1-2- vs. 1-3-plane shear strength, and bolt bearing response. The choice of scale, and what is or is not a fundamental failure mode has important downstream ramifications in terms of what testing is most appropriate, what test results can be pooled together in order to efficiently develop a B-basis strength knockdown, and – obviously – what failure criteria are appropriate.

2.1 Notched Compression Strength

The issue of interest regarding prediction of B-basis open hole compression (OHC) strength is whether or not the critical failure is viewed as a distinct laminate-level failure mode unto itself, or a ply-level unnotched fiber-direction failure occurring at a local stress concentration (the hole). Many companies apply failure criteria directly at the laminate level, thus capturing all residual process-induced thermal stresses and the as-manufactured state of quality in their design allowable strength test coupons. Further, practical component stress analysis does not explicitly account for stress concentrations due to holes, acceptable-size defects, free edges, etc.; so, a notched-laminate coupon test (OHC, in this case) is the most straightforward way to measure a directly-applicable design allowable strength. Other companies prefer to develop statistically-based design allowables at the ply-level using unnotched unidirectional or cross-ply specimens and then apply empirical factors to account for all the above-noted effects. Still others use unnotched laminate compression (UNC) tests to derive unnotched ply

strength, and then account for (only) open-hole effects separately. Figure 1 illustrates these various approaches to notched compressive strength prediction at these various length-scales, as well as how aircraft-level loads lead to laminate-level stresses.

2.2 Shear Strength

Figure 2 illustrates that, theoretically, 1-2- and 1-3-plane tape material responses should be identical, save perhaps for a difference in thermal residual stress in a multidirectional laminate. However, due to the fact that transverse matrix cracking within a ply (1-2 plane) is generally considered non-detrimental deformation, from a design/certification standpoint, but delamination (1-3 plane) is considered a failure mode, these two shear strength failure modes are treated differently.

2.3 Bearing Strength

At a somewhat larger structural scale, the B-basis strength capability of a well-designed bolted joint may be viewed as either a laminate-level or sub-element-level failure event. The multiple failure modes inherent in a bolted joint are illustrated in Figure 3. Depending on how much of this complex behavior one wants to explicitly model versus how much one can bury in the design allowable strength, various types of testing and statistical analysis are appropriate.

In order to focus this discussion on the bearing-critical failure aspects of this problem, it first must be acknowledged that composites exhibit an interaction of bearing and by-pass failure modes, and that this may be accounted for either via bearing/by-pass interaction testing and interaction equations/curves for MS-determination [1], or detailed theoretical modeling [3][4]. That said, the focus of this discussion is on the bearing-critical portion of the joint behavior and thus only involves bearing failure modes in composite skin and/or sub-structure, and the related bolt response.

Figure 4 illustrates the two practical length-scale choices for joint bearing strength failure criteria and allowables development. Either the analyst separately addresses the skin bearing, sub-structure-bearing (often metallic) and bolt failure modes; or

the MS's are written at the sub-element joint level and the various permutations of skin and sub-structure stiffness and thickness, bolt type, bolt diameter, shim type/thickness, edge-distance, etc. must be built into the design allowable methodology and testing.

3 Test Method Issues

Composite lamina and laminate test methods are a surprisingly complex and nuanced field that has evolved tremendously over the past 40 years and continues to change as materials, understanding of material behavior, and uses of the data evolve. The following three sub-sections detail the test-method issues that are relevant to the overall discussion of appropriate B-basis allowables development.

3.1 Compression Testing

Both notched and unnotched compression test methods have developed to the point that now subtle differences in panel quality and boundary conditions can (a) be exploited, while (b) confounding comparisons between notched and unnotched behavior.

If one is interested in laminate-level OHC failure modes, mean, and B-basis strengths it is a simple matter to observe that for the (0/45/90) laminate family², the failure mode is almost always the same [5], the mean strengths vary with ply percentage and environment, and the B-basis statistical strength retention (allowable / mean) is in the 0.82 – 0.95 range shown in Table 2. The between-lab precision for the ASTM D6484 OHC test method is 3.5 – 4.3% [6]. Note that, in Table 2, the difference between the two (25/50/25) laminate stacks (L1 and L1a) was only 2%, thus this difference is well within the inherent test method uncertainty.

On the other hand, if one prefers to develop unnotched allowable strengths, then a variety of test methods issues must be confronted. These issues are described in Table 3. While conservative allowables are preferred, up to a point, it is not uncommon for D695 and D6641 unnotched results to be lower than

² (%0° plies / %±45° plies / %90° plies) with at least 7% in each of the four fiber directions, thus preventing in-plane matrix failures.

filled-hole compression strength for certain materials and lay-ups. Regarding the process of backing ply strength out of multi-directional laminate test data [1] (which assumes a Maximum Stress failure criterion), the choice of laminate can make a big difference. Unnotched mean and B-Basis ply-level compression strengths from two different laminates are tabulated in Table 4, showing that the effective ply strength in a (0/45/90) laminate is 17 – 25% higher than that measured in a cross-ply laminate. Clearly, an engineering judgment call is ultimately required regarding which of the various test methods and lay-ups are the most appropriate for unnotched compression allowable strength development.

3.2 Shear Testing

In-plane and interlaminar shear response, and related test methods, have long been the subject of emotional debate. Much of the debate has centered on development of a uniform state of shear stress in the gage region of the test specimen. ASTM D2344 interlaminar shear (ILS) stress state is known to be very complex, particularly for multi-directional laminates, while ASTM D5379 in the 1-3-plane is relatively pure. For in-plane shear (IPS) stress, ASTM D3518 (a $[\pm 45]_2s$ laminate loaded in tension) yields combined tension and shear, while D4255, D5379, and D7078 yield closer approximations of pure shear stress.

Table 5 illustrates that D2344 and D5379 data yield mean ILS strengths within 10-17%, at least for one tape material system (with D2344 yielding the higher result), while a multi-directional laminate tested per D2344 (technically, out of scope, and with a more complex state of stress) is biased some 20% lower, at least at CTA and RTA conditions. Others have observed even less difference between D2344 and D5379 for 1-3-plane ILS measurement [8].

For IPS strength, measured per ASTM D3518 prior work [9] has illustrated both a question regarding definition of “failure” (specimen rupture vs an engineering definition of a set strain off-set, such as 5% as now used in all ASTM Committee D30 shear test methods); and a strong dependence of strength on ply thickness, laminate stack, and overall thickness. Table 6 shows virtually no difference between the specimen rupture and 5% strain offset

definitions of IPS strength for this particular carbon/epoxy material (tested exactly per ASTM D3518, which specifies a $[\pm 45]_2s$ laminate in order to control the effects noted in [9]), though larger differences have been observed on other materials. Also, several different ASTM test methods exist to measure IPS strength, and bias between the various methods has been suggested by others [10]. Overall, test method bias and scale effects can yield significant uncertainty in IPS strength B-basis design allowables (if IPS is considered a failure mode of interest).

3.3 Bearing Testing

As noted earlier, the main issue with bolted joint behavior involves the definition of length-scale and failure mode. However, the choice of a proper test methodology for the assumed length-scale is exceedingly important, given that measured bearing strength varies tremendously with specimen geometry. As can be seen in Table 7 and Figure 5, changes in load-reaction, joint geometry, bolt type, and environment lead to failure mode changes and statistically significant ($> 5\%$) differences in bearing strength. Figure 6 shows a typical single-bolt bearing load vs hole elongation curve. Obviously, this response is highly nonlinear, leading to a variety of definitions of what is “failure” and/or “non-detrimental deformation.” The shape of this curve is also a strong function of laminate, extensometer location, and other joint details. While not explicitly shown in Table 7, bolt torque also affects measured bearing strength and degree of nonlinearity and, given that torque-induced bolt preload relaxes over time (due to through-thickness creep in composite and shim materials), torque values less than specified installation torque – but greater than zero – are typically used for bearing allowable-strength testing. Note also that differences in tensile and compressive bearing reaction are often more than shown in the one Table 7 example; and failure mode changes from bearing to shear-out at short edge-distances.

4 Failure Criteria and Statistical Methods

As noted in the introduction, B-basis allowables development must be done in concert with the particular failure criteria and stress methodology

used by the analyst to write Margins of Safety (MS). The following cases are considered:

- Notched compression strength that either is or is not directly related to unnotched strength;
- Alternate assumptions regarding in-plane and interlaminar shear strengths; and
- Bearing as a distinct material failure mode vs. an overall joint-failure criterion.

Of note here is the fact that practical airframe strength analysis does not actually attempt to predict failure but, rather, the absence of it. Thus, task simplification is often traded against degree of conservatism.

4.1 Notched Compression Allowables

If laminate-level OHC is considered a distinct failure mode, then statistically-based allowable strengths must be developed directly from OHC test data, usually over a predetermined range of a laminate family or families. Given that the failure mode generally remains the same, statistical pooling across both laminates and environments is possible. If, on the other hand, 0-deg ply-level compression is considered to be the failure mode of interest, then (a) analytical stress methods must account for the localized stress state in each 0-deg layer (could be multiple plies) in a multidirectional laminate; and (b) statistically-based allowables must be developed for the unnotched compression strength of a 0-deg ply (perhaps also accounting for layer thickness and residual thermal stresses due to being in a multi-directional laminate). Table 8 compares and contrasts, in a notional sense (given the lack of acceptance of the recommended test matrices in [1], and wide program-to-program variations), the testing and stress analysis method requirements of these two approaches. The OHC method requires fewer coupons.

Unnotched and open hole compressive strength mean and B-basis statistical results are shown in Table 4 and Table 2, respectively. Assuming all other design factors to be equal (they are typically ratios of mean values), it is seen that for this particular tape material the OHC allowable would yield the highest ratio of B-basis-to-mean strength (82 – 95% for OHC vs. 75 – 88% for UNC).

4.2 In-Plane and Interlaminar Shear Allowables

If IPS-induced matrix micro-cracks are deemed to be non-detrimental damage in multi-directional laminates, then such a shear MS need not be written (or the “allowable strength” be set sufficiently high such that other failure modes always occur first). This IPS allowable strength is still necessary for all-bias laminates, and in such cases should be suitably conservative since there are no fibers to carry ultimate load. Table 6 illustrates a small portion of possible B-Basis allowable strength outcomes for this case. Different test methods would extend it further.

For ILS strength prediction, the foremost consideration is to first choose an appropriate failure criterion. If a laminate-level criterion is used, then it must be matched with laminate-level allowable test specimens. If ply-level analysis is done, then either ply properties must be backed out of laminate-level specimens, or ply-level tests done and residual thermal effects explicitly accounted for. If an ILT-ILS interaction failure criterion is used, testing which interrogates a range of tensile/shear stress ratios should be used to empirically correlate it. If a fracture-based criterion is used, an entirely different set of analysis methods/tools and coupon-level energy-based allowable testing is required. For the specific use of the Maximum Stress failure criterion with either ply- or laminate-level allowables, Table 5 shows that the B-basis ILS strength can vary by as much as 67% for a given environment.

4.3 Bolted Joint Allowables

Table 9 illustrates the different types of testing required, depending on whether one chooses to generate bolted joint bearing allowable strengths on a laminate/bolt/substructure level, or sub-element joint level. Clearly, the practicality of one vs. the other approach depends on how many different joint configurations are anticipated. Also, the laminate/bolt-level approach allows for a larger statistical pool upon which to base B-basis allowables. The author is not aware of any back-to-back comparisons between these two approaches, in terms of relative joint and/or analysis cost-efficiency.

A separate issue is the definition of “bearing” failure. Many companies choose to define it very conservatively and then not explicitly consider many of the joint-geometry effects noted in Table 9. While this is cost-effective from an allowables-development standpoint, it leads to over-predicting the bearing failure mode and under-predicting the bolt failure mode, which is undesirable from a damage tolerance and safety standpoint.

5 Summary

In summary, the objective of this paper was to demonstrate the complexity of test-method-induced effects on B-basis allowable strengths, and how that interacts with failure mode definitions and length-scale/failure criteria-specific issues to influence the reliability and accuracy of composite strength predictions. Three relevant properties: compression, shear, and bearing; are offered as examples. Salient observations include:

- It is often simpler and more straightforward to perform strength analysis (and experimentally generate design allowables) at relatively higher length-scales, given that ply-level analysis and testing is fraught with large uncertainty and error (thus yielding lower B-basis allowables and requiring extensive laminate- and sub-element-level correlation, anyway);
- Understanding which failure modes are critical and which are non-detrimental, from a structural certification standpoint, is of fundamental importance in methods and allowables development; and
- Coupon-level test methods vary widely in reliability, and significant bias can exist between different methods of measuring the same property.

In addition to notched compression, shear, and bearing, other composite strength properties exhibit similar interactions and statistical allowable-development issues. It is hoped that readers of this paper will gain a better appreciation of the engineering judgment and material-specific choices that are required in the development of structural design allowables for production aircraft use.

References

- [1] *Composite Materials Handbook-17, Vol. 1, Guidelines for Characterization of Structural Materials*, SAE International April, 2012.
- [2] P. Grant and A. Sawicki “Development of design and analysis methodology for composite bolted joints,” Proceedings, *AHS National Technical Specialists Meeting on Rotorcraft Structures*, Williamsburg, VA, October, 1991.
- [3] M. Waddoups, J. Eisenmann and B. Kaminski “Macroscopic fracture mechanics of advanced composite materials,” *J. Comp Mat’l*, v5, October, 1971, pp 446-454.
- [4] J. Eisenmann and C. Rousseau “IBOLT: a composite bolted joint static strength prediction tool,” *Joining and Repair of Composite Structures, ASTM STP 1455*, pp 161-181, 2004
- [5] H. Bau, D. Hoyt and C. Rousseau “Open hole compression strength and failure characterization in carbon/epoxy tape laminates” *Composite Structures: Theory and Practice, STP 1383*, pp 273-292, 2000.
- [6] Annual Book of ASTM Standards, Vol. 15.03, www.astm.org, 2013.
- [7] J. Berg and D. Adams “An evaluation of composite material compression test methods” *J. Comp Tech & Res*, v11, n2, pp 41-46, 1989.
- [8] A. Makeev, Y. He, P. Carpentier and B. Shonkwiler “A method for measurement of multiple constitutive properties for composite materials” *Comp: Part A*, 43, pp 2199-2210, 2012.
- [9] S. Kellas, J. Morton and K. Jackson “Damage and failure mechanisms in scaled angle-ply laminates” *Composite Materials: Fatigue and Fracture, 4th Volume, ASTM STP 1156*, pp 257-280, 1993.
- [10] D. Adams and E. Lewis, “Current status of composite material shear test methods” *SAMPE J.*, v31, n6, pp 32-40, Jan/Feb 1994.
- [11] MMPDS-07 *Metallic Materials Properties Development and Standardization (MMPDS) Handbook*, Apr 2012.

Table 1. Composite Failure Modes

<i>Constituent Length-Scale</i>	
Fiber Tension	Fiber Compression
Matrix Tension	Fiber-Matrix Interface Tension
Matrix Compression	Fiber-Matrix Interface Shear
<i>Unidirectional Ply Length-Scale</i>	
Axial Ply Tension	Transverse Ply Tension
Axial Ply Compression	Transverse Ply Compression
1-2- and 1-3-Plane Shear	2-3-Plane Shear
Interlaminar Tension	Interlaminar Compression
Mode I Interlaminar Fracture	Mixed-Mode Interlaminar Fracture
<i>Multi-Directional Laminate Length-Scale</i>	
Laminate Unnotched Tension	Laminate Unnotched Compression
Laminate Notched Tension	Laminate Notched Compression
Bearing-with-Tension Reaction	Bearing-with-Compression Reaction
Bearing-with-Shear Reaction	Tension Bearing/By-Pass Interaction
Compression Bearing/By-Pass Interaction	Fastener Pull-Thru
ILT/ILS Interaction	Sub-Laminate Buckling/Compression Interaction
<i>Structural Length-Scales</i>	
Beam-Column Buckling	Crippling
Shell Buckling	Energy Absorption
Lug Strength	Complex Bolted Joints
Complex Bonded Joints	Flange Bending
Cutouts	Sandwich Details

Table 2. OHC Strengths for Various Laminates

Value	Test Environment			
	CTA	RTA	ETW1	ETW2
[±45/0/±45/90/±45/±45]s (10/80/10)				
Carbon/Epoxy Tape Laminate				
No. of Lots	3	3	3	3
No. Coupons	18	18	18	18
Mean (ksi)	40.3	36.0	29.0	25.7
CV (%)	7.26	5.12	3.42	3.82
B-Basis (ksi)	34.5	32.4	27.0	23.8
B-Basis / Mean	0.857	0.899	0.932	0.925
L1 = [45/0/-45/90]3s (25/50/25)				
Carbon/Epoxy Tape Laminate				
No. of Lots	3	3	4	3
No. Coupons	17	18	21	18
Mean (ksi)	48.9	42.9	35.3	31.9
CV (%)	3.58	2.44	3.07	3.42
B-Basis (ksi)	45.4	40.8	33.3	29.8
B-Basis / Mean	0.928	0.952	0.941	0.932
L1a = [45/90/-45/0]3s (25/50/25)				
Carbon/Epoxy Tape Laminate				
No. of Lots		1		
No. Coupons		3		
Mean (ksi)		43.6		
CV (%)		3.83		
L1 / L1a		0.983		
[0/0/45/0/90/-45/0/45/0/-45]s (50/40/10)				
Carbon/Epoxy Tape Laminate				
No. of Lots	3	3	3	3
No. Coupons	18	18	18	18
Mean (ksi)	64.6	53.2	50.0	39.7
CV (%)	6.12	8.92	5.05	6.55
B-Basis (ksi)	56.8	43.8	45.1	34.6
B-Basis / Mean	0.879	0.824	0.900	0.871
Notes:				
All failures net-section compression.				
CTA = cold-temperature, ambient				
RTA = room-temperature, ambient				
ETW1 = elevated-temperature, wet (intermediate)				
ETW2 = elevated-temperature, wet (high)				

Table 3. Unnotched Compression Strength Test Method Issues

Test Method	Uni-Tape	[90/0]ns Tape and Fabric	(0/45/90) Laminate
SACMA SRM 1R-94	Relatively high result due to short 0.188-inch gage length Some end-failures	Gage length too short for some fabric unit-cell-sizes Some end-failures	Not appropriate (gage length too short)
ASTM D695	Not appropriate (splitting at radii)	Not for 0/90 tape (splitting at radii) Acceptable for fabric	Not for tape laminates (splitting at radii)
ASTM D3410	Complex, hard to use fixtures May require trial-and-error (tabs, specimen thickness) to get repeatable results		
ASTM D6641	Requires tabbing (Proc B) May require trial-and-error	Relatively low result, compared to SRM 1R-94 May require trial-and-error (bolt torque) to get good results	
ASTM D6484 (no hole)	Not appropriate (end-failures would be likely) Technically, un-notched is out-of-scope per test method		Relatively high result (but out-of-scope)
Overall, it is not uncommon to see >10% between-method bias if multiple test methods are used [7]. Incorrect failure modes and relatively high CV's are not uncommon.			

Table 4. Unnotched Compression Strengths

Value	Test Environment			
	CTA	RTA	ETW1	ETW2
F11 cu backed out of [90/0]4s D6641 Tests				
No. of Lots	2	2	2	2
No. Coupons	10	8	6	9
Mean (ksi)	220.9	189.4	159.2	147.1
CV (%)	8.84	9.69	6.62	9.90
B-Basis (ksi)	174.9	142.0	127.5	111.4
B-Basis / Mean	0.792	0.750	0.801	0.757
F11 cu backed out of (25/50/25) laminate D6641 Tests				
No. of Lots	3	4	1	6
No. Coupons	18	15	3	31
Mean (ksi)	266.8	252.7	200.0	177.1
CV (%)	6.77	5.63	2.16	6.60
B-Basis (ksi)	231.2	223.3		156.4
B-Basis / Mean	0.866	0.884		0.883
Ratios of [90/0] to (25/50/25) Values				
Mean	0.83	0.75	0.80	0.83
B-Basis	0.76	0.64		0.71
Notes: All failures net-section compression.				

Table 5. Comparison of 1-3-Plane ILS Strengths

Value	Test Environment			
	CTA	RTA	ETW1	ETW2
F13su per D2344, [0]16				
No. of Lots	3	3	3	3
No. Coupons	20	22	18	19
Mean (ksi)	20.3	14.8	8.54	6.92
CV (%)	6.28	3.48	2.24	4.10
B-Basis (ksi)	17.9	13.8	8.16	6.37
B-Basis / Mean	0.879	0.934	0.956	0.920
F13su per D2344, [45/90/-45/0]3s				
No. of Lots	3	3		5
No. Coupons	18	12		23
Mean (ksi)	13.0	10.2		5.97
CV (%)	8.10	8.59		2.50
B-Basis (ksi)	10.9	8.28		5.69
B-Basis / Mean	0.840	0.810		0.953
Ratios of Uni-tape to Laminate Values				
Mean	1.57	1.45		1.16
B-Basis	1.64	1.67		1.12
F13su per D5379				
No. of Lots	1	1		1
No. Coupons	6	7		7
Mean (ksi)	17.4	12.9		6.31
CV (%)	2.08	1.49		2.17
Ratios of D2344 to D5379 Values				
Uni-lay-up	1.17	1.15		1.10
Laminate	0.74	0.79		0.95
Notes: All failures ILS.				

Table 6. Comparison of In-Plane Shear Strengths

Value	Test Environment			
	CTA	RTA	ETW1	ETW2
F12su-5% off-set				
No. of Lots	2	2	2	2
No. Coupons	21	18	18	18
Mean (ksi)	13.3	9.63	5.48	4.56
CV (%)	8.06	8.71	6.93	5.40
B-Basis (ksi)	11.3	7.98	4.73	4.07
B-Basis / Mean	0.846	0.828	0.863	0.893
F12su-max				
No. of Lots	2	2	2	2
No. Coupons	37	18	18	18
Mean (ksi)	12.8	9.80	5.53	4.59
CV (%)	9.71	8.80	6.68	5.19
B-Basis (ksi)	10.6	8.10	4.80	4.12
B-Basis / Mean	0.833	0.826	0.868	0.897
Ratios of 5% -off-set to max				
Mean	1.04	0.98	0.99	0.99
B-Basis	1.06	0.99	0.98	0.99
<u>Notes:</u> All failures IPS.				

Table 7. Comparison of Bearing Strengths with Various Boundary Constraints

Value	Test Environment			
	CTA	RTA	ETW1	ETW2
(25/50/25) Double-Shear Bearing, Tension				
No. of Lots		1		
No. Coupons		6		
Mean (ksi)		215.6		
CV (%)		4.14		
B-Basis (ksi)		188.8		
B-Basis / Mean		0.876		
(25/50/25) Double-Shear Bearing, Compr				
No. of Lots	3	3	3	3
No. Coupons	10	10	6	21
Mean (ksi)	224.9	216.7	172.5	169.0
CV (%)	4.89	3.02	5.78	4.09
B-Basis (ksi)	199.0	201.2	142.5	155.9
B-Basis / Mean	0.885	0.929	0.826	0.922
(25/50/25) Single-Shear Bearing, Tension				
No. of Lots	3	3	3	2
No. Coupons	10	10	6	4
Mean (ksi)	157.8	143.9	121.5	118.9
CV (%)	2.27	3.44	4.77	4.11
B-Basis (ksi)	149.3	132.2	104.0	98.60
B-Basis / Mean	0.946	0.919	0.857	0.829
(25/50/25) Single-Shear Bearing, Ti Bolt				
No. of Lots		3		3
No. Coupons		19		18
Mean (ksi)		128.5		106.7
CV (%)		4.42		4.48
B-Basis (ksi)		117.5		97.27
B-Basis / Mean		0.914		0.911
Ratios of Tension to Compression Reaction				
Mean		1.00		
B-Basis		0.94		
Ratios of Single to Double Shear Reaction				
Mean	0.70	0.66	0.70	0.70
B-Basis	0.75	0.66	0.73	
Ratios of Fbru for 160-ksi to 260-ksi Bolt				
Mean		0.89		0.90
<u>Notes:</u> All failures laminate bearing except 160-ksi Ti bolt (bolt yielding).				

Table 8. Comparison of Compression Allowable Test Matrices

Value	Test Environment			
	CTA	RTA	ETW1	ETW2
OHC Allowables Test Matrix				
No. of Lots	1	3	3	3
No. Lay-Ups	3	3	1	3
No. Coupons	3	3	3	3
Total	9	27	9	27
N = 72 when pooled across both environments and laminates.				
kt * UNC Test Matrix				
UNC Test				
No. of Lots	1	3	3	3
No. Lay-Ups	3	3	1	3
No. Coupons	6	6	6	6
OHC Test				
No. of Lots	1	1	1	1
No. Lay-Ups	3	3	1	3
No. Coupons	3	3	3	3
Total	27	63	21	63
N = 18-24 if only pooling UNC across environments but not laminates.				
Notes: Fewer coupon replicates/condition required for OHC vs. UNC, due to higher OHC repeatability and lower CVs.				

Table 9. Comparison of Bolted Joint Test Matrices

<u>Laminate/Bolt/Sub-Structure-Level Analysis</u>						
Skin/Sub-Structure Laminate			Bolt			
	Brg-Tens	Brg-Compr	Fsu	Ftu	F head	F thread
Lots	3	3	5	5	1	1
Lay-Ups	6	6				
Coupons	3	3	5	5	5	5
Total	54	54	25	25	5	5
Notes: Repeat for 3 or 4 environments N = 162 – 216 when pooled across laminates and environments.			Notes: Repeat for each D (typically 3 – 5) and bolt type (typically at least 4). Base alloy Temperature Reduction Factor used for environmental effects. N = 75 – 175/bolt type (often provided by fastener supplier)			
For metallic sub-structure, all necessary static allowables are assumed to be available from MMPDS [11].						
<u>Sub-Element-Level Joint Analysis</u>						
	Brg-Tens	Brg-Compr	Notes			
Baseline Joint	18	18	3 mat'l lots, 6 coupons/lot, RTA			
Coupons / Configuration	6	6	1 mat'l lot+			
Configurations	Non-RTA environments (2-3), D (3-5), bolt types (4+), D/t (3+), e/D (3+), w/D (3+), shim thicknesses (3+), bolt-to-hole-clearance (2+)					
Total	N = 36 baseline, 360 – 720 configurations					

Reduction of Aircraft Loads to Laminate-Level Stresses

Failure Criteria Options

Ply-Level

$$MS = F_{11cu} / k_{t1} * \sigma_{11c} - 1.0$$

σ_{11c} from CLPT

$$k_{t1} = F_{11cu} / F_{ohc}$$

F_{11cu} & F_{ohc} measured

Un-notched Laminate

$$MS = F_{unc} / k_{t2} * \sigma_{xxc} - 1.0$$

σ_{xxc} from shell model

$$k_{t2} = F_{unc} / F_{ohc}$$

F_{unc} & F_{ohc} measured

Notched Laminate

$$MS = F_{ohc} / \sigma_{xxc} - 1.0$$

F_{ohc} measured

(could be strain instead of stress)

Figure 1. Notched Compression Strength Prediction at Various Length-Scales

Figure 2. 1-2 and 1-3 Plane Shear Stresses

- | | |
|---|---|
| <p><u>Bolt Failure Modes</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Head/drive-feature fracture Head/shank yielding Shank shear Thread bending Thread tension Nut tension | <p><u>Composite Failure Modes</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Bearing Net tension Shear tear-out Pull-through Edge delamination |
|---|---|

Metallic substructure exhibits different unique failure modes

Figure 3. Bolted Joint Behavior

Figure 4. Bolted Joint Length-Scale Choices

Figure 5. Effect of Design Parameters on Single-Shear Bearing Strength

Figure 6. Typical Single-Bolt Bearing Response